

Formation and stability of heterobinuclear complexes containing Hg^{II} and divalent metal ions with EDTA and CDTA

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Manuscript received 27 May 2004, revised 5 October 2005, accepted 27 October 2005

Abstract : The stability constants for the heterobinuclear complexes of the type HgLM (L = EDTA or CDTA (*trans*-1,2-diaminocyclohexane tetracetic acid) and M = Be, Mg, Ca, Pb, Cd, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu) have been determined by computer analysis of the pH titration data. The results are discussed to obtain the solution structures of the above mixed-metal complexes.

Keywords : Stability constants, divalent metal ions, EDTA, CDTA.

The present paper describes the complexation equilibria of the heterobinuclear Hg^{II}-M^{II} EDTA and CDTA complexes (M^{II} = Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}) in aqueous solution by potentiometric method at 37 °C and *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃). The stability constants have been evaluated using SCOGS¹ computer program.

Results and discussion

The hexadentate nature of EDTA in its complexes was confirmed by the infrared spectral studies by Busch and Bailar². The complexes of CDTA in solution have been investigated by ¹H NMR spectroscopy³ and reported that CDTA behaves as a pentadentate ligand with one free carboxylate group.

For the evaluation of stability constants of mixed-metal complexes by the SCOGS program, the complex formation has been assumed to take place according to :

$$\beta_{pqrt} = \frac{[(M_1)_p (M_2)_q (L)_r (OH)_t]}{[M_1]^p [M_2]^q [L]^r [OH]^t}$$

where, L = EDTA/CDTA, M₁ = Hg^{II} and M₂ = other M^{II} ions. p, q, r and t are stoichiometric numbers; p, q and r are usually positive number or zero, t is a negative number for a protonic species and a positive number for a hydroxo species. Preliminary estimates of binary and ternary constants obtained by least square method⁴, used

as input data for running the SCOGS program. The plot of % concentration against pH gives the distribution curves of the species formed. Mixed-metal complexes, Hg^{II}-EDTA/CDTA-M^{II} are found to be the major species in the (1 : 1 : 1) Hg²⁺ : L⁴⁻ : M²⁺ systems along with the binary ones. Formation of hydroxo species viz. M(OH)⁺ and M(OH)₂ have been taken into consideration in calculating the formation constants since the buffer regions corresponding to the metal-ligand complex formation equilibria are found to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of M²⁺(aq) ions. Rise in the concentration of hydroxo species with concomitant decline in the concentrations of the binary and ternary complexes at pH > 3.5 gives indication of the hydrolytic equilibria (1) and (2)

The plots indicate that formation of heterobinuclear complex starts from very low pH values and concentration increases with increase of pH. Further, the deprotonation of carboxylate groups of EDTA and CDTA in the mixed-metal systems takes place generally at pH ~ 1.5 to 3.5 and the maximum concentration of complex species have been found in this pH range. But it has been reported⁵ that in the mixed-ligand systems, the deprotonation takes place beyond pH ~ 3-4. This demonstrates that the mixed-metal complex formation is preferred as compared to mixed-ligand systems. However, as pointed out by Amico *et al.*⁶, it is not possible to know in advance which way electronic and stereochemical properties of different metal ions will affect the stabilities of the mixed-metal complex

Table 1. Proton-ligand constants, hydrolytic constants and M^{II} -ligand binary constants in aqueous solution at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaNO}_3$

(a) Proton-ligand formation constants :

	$\log \beta_{001-1}$	$\log \beta_{001-2}$	$\log \beta_{001-3}$	$\log \beta_{001-4}$
EDTA	10.74	17.40	20.56	23.06
CDTA	13.40	20.55	24.90	28.30

(b) Hydrolytic constants of M^{2+} (aq) ions :

$\log \beta_{1001}$	$\log \beta_{0101}$				
	Be	Cd	Mn	Ni	Cu
Hg					
-3.84	-5.70	-9.60	-0.02	-4.30	-6.10
$\log \beta_{1002}$	$\log \beta_{0102}$				
-6.38	-5.50	-	-	-	-

(c) M^{II} -ligand binary constants :

	$\log \beta_{101-2}$					$\log \beta_{011-2}$				
	Hg	Be	Mg	Ca	Pb	Cd	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu
EDTA	21.96	9.2	8.88	10.61	17.88	16.36	13.81	16.26	18.52	18.70
CDTA	23.50	11.51	-	-	20.24	19.84	17.43	19.58	20.20	21.00

formation.

The proton-ligand formation constants of EDTA and CDTA have been determined by Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁴ and are presented in Table 1. The values reported herein are in consistency with the literature values⁷.

The overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) of the heterobimetallic complexes with EDTA and CDTA have been presented in Table 2.

Hg^{II}-EDTA-M^{II} systems : The overall stability constants of Hg^{II}-EDTA-M^{II} systems follow the order : Hg^{II}-Cd^{II} < Hg^{II}-Mg^{II} < Hg^{II}-Pb^{II} < Hg^{II}-Ca^{II} < Hg^{II}-Mn^{II} < Hg^{II}-Co^{II} < Hg^{II}-Ni^{II} < Hg^{II}-Be^{II} < Hg^{II}-Cu^{II}. The binary H₂Hg^{II}-EDTA complex is expected to involve four-

coordinate tetrahedral arrangement⁸ in which Hg^{II} is expected to bound to two amino nitrogen atoms and two carboxylate O-atoms. The complex may coordinate another metal ion using the two uncoordinated -COOH groups forming the heterobinuclear complexes Hg^{II}-EDTA-M^{II}. The remaining coordinating sites on the metal ions of the ternary complexes may be satisfied by solvent H₂O molecules.

Hg^{II}-CDTA-M^{II} systems : The overall stability constants of Hg^{II}-CDTA-M^{II} complexes follow the order : Hg^{II}-Co^{II} < Hg^{II}-Cd^{II} < Hg^{II}-Mn^{II} < Hg^{II}-Be^{II}, Hg^{II}-Ni^{II} < Hg^{II}-Cu^{II} < Hg^{II}-Pb^{II}. The stereochemistry of CDTA chelates is quite similar to that of EDTA chelates². When CDTA coordinates with Hg^{II}, it is safely presumed that Hg^{II} is occupying four coordination sites of the ligand i.e. two carboxyl and two amino N atoms, thus forming 1 : 1 metal ligand binary complex. With the remaining coordination groups of the coordinated ligand the binary complex may bind other M^{II} ions, forming the heterobimetallic complexes. Solvent H₂O molecules may coordinate with the vacant coordination sites of the metal ions in the mixed-metal complexes, which is evident from the stereochemistry⁹ of the compounds like Na₂Mg^{II}-EDTA.xH₂O, Ba^{II}-Cu^{II}-EDTA.5H₂O, Na₃Ca^{II}-DTPA. H₂O.

The higher stability of the metal chelates of *trans*-CDTA over those of EDTA is explained by the fact that during chelation, the carbon chain between the nitrogen atoms in EDTA has to be rotated to bring the nitrogen atoms in a favourable position for chelation. In *trans*-CDTA, there is a restriction of the rotation of the carbon

Table 2. Stability constants for the heterobinuclear Hg^{II}-L-M^{II} systems at 37 °C. and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaNO}_3$

M^{II}	$\log \beta_{1110}$	
	Hg ^{II} -EDTA-M ^{II}	Hg ^{II} -CDTA-Hg ^{II}
Be ^{II}	25.50	27.49
Mg ^{II}	23.20	-
Ca ^{II}	23.50	-
Pb ^{II}	23.22	28.90
Cd ^{II}	22.88	26.40
Mn ^{II}	23.52	27.40
Co ^{II}	24.24	26.06
Ni ^{II}	24.91	28.20
Cu ^{II}	25.56	28.40

Standard deviations : $\pm(0.1 \sim 0.5)$ in log units.

chain. but, since the ligand nitrogen atoms are placed very close to each other, very little orientation is necessary for chelation to occur². The ternary $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}\text{-M}^{\text{II}}\text{-EDTA/CDTA}$ complexes formed by both the ligands i.e. EDTA and CDTA with the metal ions of the first transition series follow the Irving-Williams order : $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{II}} < \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}\text{-Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$. Be^{II} being the smallest in size has the highest value of stability constant in the ternary systems.

Experimental

Solutions of Hg^{II} , Be^{II} , Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} nitrate were prepared and standardized by EDTA titrations¹⁰. 0.1 M solutions of EDTA and CDTA were prepared by dissolving the ligands into two equivalents of standard NaOH solution, which was prepared in double distilled water and standardised against a standard oxalic acid solution. Solutions of carbonate free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) and nitric acid (A.R.) were standardised potentiometrically. A digital pH-meter, reproducibility of ± 0.01 pH (century-model-CP 901-S) with a glass saturated calomel electrode system was used to determine the pH values.

Four reaction mixtures (i-iv) were prepared by keeping the total volume 50 ml in each case and the molar ratio of ligand : Hg^{II} : M^{II} ions undertaken was 1 : 1 : 1 : (i) 10 ml NaNO_3 (0.5 mol dm^{-3}) + 10 ml HNO_3 (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 30 ml H_2O . (ii) 10 ml NaNO_3 (0.5 mol dm^{-3}) + 10 ml HNO_3 (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 5 ml EDTA/CDTA (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 25 ml H_2O . (iii) 10 ml NaNO_3 (0.5 mol dm^{-3}) + 10 ml HNO_3 (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 5 ml EDTA/CDTA (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 5 ml Hg^{II} (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 20 ml H_2O . (iv) 10 ml NaNO_3 (0.5 mol dm^{-3}) + 10 ml HNO_3 (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 5 ml EDTA/CDTA

(0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 5 ml Hg^{II} (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 5 ml M^{II} (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) + 15 ml H_2O .

The other experimental details were the same as described elsewhere¹¹. Ionic product of water (K_w) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the above experimental conditions were obtained from literature¹².

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